

Yasynska Elvira Tsezarivna

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Social Medicine and Public Health. Bukovinian State Medical University, 58002. str. Teatralna 2, Chernivtsi, phone: 380956748935, e-mail:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3768-7278>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12800515>

ANALYSIS OF SELF-ASSESSMENT RESULTS OF OWN HEALTH OF SELECTED CONTINGENTS

Abstract.

The article analyzes the indicators of own health of selected contingents living in the city of Chernivtsi. The author used an adapted health questionnaire-36 (MOS-36 - Short-Form Health Survey, or MOS SF-36), which was first tested in the USA. The adapted questionnaire gave respondents the opportunity to give their own self-assessment of their health according to the following blocks: self-assessment of their own health; respondents' attitude to their own health; the presence of diseases; seeking medical help; self-assessment of lifestyle; respondents' awareness of a healthy lifestyle. 45% of respondents, especially (ages 20-39), do not pay attention to their health. From the male group of this age, according to their own assessment, 1 man had a bad state of health and 1 man - very bad (presence of a chronic incurable disease). 60% of respondents (40% of men and 20% of women sought medical help only when absolutely necessary and self-medicated). 12% of men and 10% of women in the age group (40-59 years) did not know about the presence of chronic diseases for several years. In addition, 30% of male respondents in two age groups (20-39 years and 40-59 years) who did not follow a healthy lifestyle rated their lifestyle as satisfactory. 70% of respondents, including people of both genders, noted strong stress and nervousness due to a full-scale war.

As a result of the conducted research, the results of awareness of the selected contingents regarding a healthy lifestyle were obtained. Most often, respondents obtained information about a healthy lifestyle from the Internet, the press, and television programs (45% of men and 32% of women of the II and III age groups) ($p \leq 0.001$). 27% of men and 15% of women of the 1st age group noted a low level of awareness about preserving their health in family doctors' offices. However, respondents of older age groups (70% of men and 65% of women) are satisfied with receiving this information. The analysis of the subjective component of health made it possible to identify certain deviations in the self-assessment of individual health and subsequently to correct the influence of adverse factors on the formation of one's own health.

Keywords: *health, contingents, self-assessment*

Introduction. It has been proven that the health of the population is one of the priority values of the state policy of any European country. In the complex characteristics of the quality of life of the population [3], the state of health of residents, the organization and efficiency of the health care system occupy an important place.

Undoubtedly, the current situation requires urgent strategic approaches aimed at reforming the health care system. Health care in all countries without exception is a priority direction of the social policy of each state and in many cases – a component of national security [5].

The health of the population is a key indicator of the social well-being of society and the effectiveness of the state's social policy. The level of public health directly depends on investments in this area and the quality of provided medical services, which, in turn, reduces morbidity and increases the duration of the productive period of life. The health of the population reflects a combination of such factors as working conditions, the state of the environment, the material and technical base of society, as well as the effectiveness of the health care system. Low population health indicators and a high level of morbidity negatively affect the quality of human life and lead to an increase in additional costs for the provision of medical services, a decrease in labor productivity, etc. [4].

Presenting main material.

At the population level, health is a multifactorial phenomenon that includes objective and subjective components. Low self-esteem of health affects the formation of risky behavior, the development of bad habits and psychological disorders. The subjective component of health makes it possible to identify certain deviations in self-esteem or to minimize the influence of adverse factors on the formation of one's own health.

Health is determined by an integral assessment of various factors. Approximately 50% of all factors affecting health are objective and are distributed as follows: the environment is approximately 25%, heredity - 18-20%, medical care - 8-10%. About 50% belong to subjective factors related to lifestyle. These factors include the mode of work and rest, physical activity or lack thereof, diet, psycho-emotional state, smoking, alcohol abuse. In addition, emphasis is placed on anti-risk factors: moderate exercise and sports, humor, benevolence, and an optimistic outlook on life.

External factors include: climate-geographical conditions, poor ecological situation, low socio-economic status, urbanization, etc.

Internal factors include: lifestyle, heredity, genetic susceptibility to diseases.

The purpose of the article: analyze and evaluate the results of self-assessment of the selected contingents using the modernized health questionnaire-36.

Materials and methods: The research was conducted by interviewing 245 people (125 men and 120

women) who living in the city of Chernivtsi. All respondents were divided into 3 age groups, including men and women (20-39 years; 40-59 years; 60-79 years). The sociological survey was based on a specially developed modernized health questionnaire-36 (MOS-36 - Short-Form Health Survey, or MOS SF-36) [1], which included the following blocks of questions:

- self-assessment of one's own health;
- respondents' attitude to their own health;
- the presence of diseases;
- seeking medical help;
- self-assessment of lifestyle;
- respondents' awareness of a healthy lifestyle.

The average age of the examined patients was 50.5 years. The questionnaire consisted of 36 questions. Each respondent's answer was evaluated in points, which were later added up and analyzed. The evaluation indicators ranged from 0 to 100, where 100 is full health. Statistical processing of the material was carried out using the χ^2 method. The difference was considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Based on the results of the sociological research, the following was established: among the respondents of the 1st age group (20-39 years old), 2 men (4.5%) and 6 women (15%) rated their state of health as "very good"; 10 (22%) and 12 (30%) women - "good"; 31 men (69.5%) and 22 women (55%) rated their health as satisfactory. From the male group of this age, according to their own assessment, 1 man (2%) had a bad state of health and 1 man (2%) – very bad. These respondents had a history of chronic diseases and 1 of them periodically abused alcohol. Gender specificities were noted in persons of this age group. None of the women in this group rated their health status as "bad" or "very bad" ($p < 0.05$). When analyzing the respondents of the II age

group (40-59 years old), only 2 women (5.7%) rated their own state of health as "very good", 7 women (20%) and 5 (16.7%) men rated their health as "good". 20 men (66.6%) and 22 women (62.8%) had a satisfactory state of health (according to their own assessment). 3 men (10%) and 2 women (5.7%) had poor health status; very bad - 2 men (6.7%) and 2 women (5.7%).

As a result of our analysis of the III group (60-79 years old), we saw changes in the direction of deterioration of their health according to the respondents' own self-assessment. Thus, none of the interviewees assessed their state of health as "very good", 2 men (4%) and 2 women (4.4%) of this age group consider their state of health to be good. 34 men (68%) and 35 women (77.8%) had a satisfactory state of health (according to their own assessment). 10 men (20%) and 6 women (13.3%) had poor health; 4 men (8%) and 2 women (4.4%) - considered their state of health to be "very bad" ($p < 0.01$).

Assessing their health status using the health formula, respondents were able to determine their risks and anti-risks and make the necessary adjustments.

Considering the fact that low self-esteem of health is a factor influencing its formation in young people, their choice of risky behavior, predisposition to harmful habits and psychological disorders, it is important to take into account the subjective component of health in teenagers and young people with the aim of early detection of certain deviations in self-esteem or the influence of adverse factors on the formation of health, the effect of which can be minimized.

Therefore, it is extremely important to emphasize the subjective components of health. This allows you to minimize the effect of adverse risk factors and detect certain deviations in self-esteem in a timely manner.

Table 1

Results of respondents' self-assessment of health

Age of respondents		20-39 years old				40-59 years old				60-79 years old			
		males		females		males		females		males		females	
Gender of respondents		abs	%	abs	%	abs	%	abs	%	abs	%	abs	%
State respondents' health	Very good	2	4.5	6	15	0	0	2	5.7	0	0	0	0
	Good	10	22	12	30	5	16.7	7	20	2	4	2	4.4
	Satisfactory	31	69.5	22	55	20	66.6	22	62.8	34	68	35	77.8
	Bad	1	2	0	0	3	10	2	5.7	10	20	6	13.3
	Very bad	1	2	0	0	2	6.7	2	5.7	4	8	2	4.4
In total		45	100	40	100	30	100	35	100	50	100	45	100

The respondents received information about a healthy lifestyle from the Internet, television programs, and the press (45% of men and 32% of women of II and III age groups) ($p \leq 0.001$). The analysis of awareness of a healthy lifestyle by respondents in the age group of 20-39 years showed that 27% of men and 15% of women noted a low level of awareness of maintaining their health in outpatient clinics. Respondents in the 60-79 age group (70% of men and 65% of women) are satisfied with receiving this information. To the question "Are you satisfied with the promotion of a healthy lifestyle in medical institutions?" 46% of men in the 1-st age group (20-39 years) answered that rather "No". But the respondents of the older age group 970% (45% of men and 55% of women) gave a positive answer.

Conclusion.

Regardless of the stage of life, the improvement of self-esteem of health must be achieved through the improvement of the social environment and the implementation of the principles of a healthy lifestyle. This includes various forms of self-realization (regular physical education, moderate sports, etc.). Inadequate self-assessment of one's own health leads to deviant forms of human behavior and the emergence of harmful habits. People's awareness of subjective risks and anti-risks of their own health gives them the opportunity to get rid of many harmful habits.

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